

Benzofuran Derivatives : Synthesis and Screening of New Benzofuran-, 3-Methylbenzofuran- and 5-Methoxybenzofuran-2-Carbamates and Carbamides

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A number of aryl benzofuran-, 3-methylbenzofuran- and 5-methoxybenzofuran-2-carbamates and carbamides have been synthesized and screened for *in vitro* antibacterial, antimycobacterial, antifungal, anti-amoebic and for *in vivo* anthelmintic activities against a variety of micro-organisms.

A number of patents have appeared in recent years describing the usefulness of various benzofuran derivatives as bactericides¹, cardiovascular², anti-pyretic, antiinflammatory, local anaesthetic and antihistaminic agents³. The synthesis, antibacterial and antifungal properties of some aryl and arylalkyl-5-nitrofurans-2-carbamates have been described earlier⁴ from these laboratories. In continuation of this work, we have prepared several new aryl benzofuran-2-carbamates and carbamides

of type I and II respectively with a view to study their antimicrobial and antiparasital activities. Some hitherto unreported aryl 3-methylbenzofuran- and 5-methoxy-benzofuran-2-carbamates have also been synthesised in order to study the effect of these two substituents on their biological activity. Recently Shafiee et al⁵ also have reported the antibacterial and antifungal activities of related alkyl and polyhalophenyl esters of 3-methylbenzofuran-2-carbamic acid.

The desired carbamates (I) and carbamides (II) were prepared by reacting the respective benzofuran-2-carboxazide with appropriate phenol or aniline and were obtained as colourless to pale yellow crystalline solids.

Experimental

All melting points were recorded in an open capillary tube and are uncorrected.

5-Methoxybenzofuran-2-carboxazide

To a cold solution of 5-methoxybenzofuran-2-carboxylic acid chloride (21.05 g) in acetone (75 ml) was added dropwise with stirring, a solution of

sodium azide (10 g) in water (100 ml), maintaining the temperature below 10°. Stirring was further continued for 4 hr at room temperature and the reaction mixture was diluted with cold water (75 ml). The colourless crystalline solid obtained was filtered, washed with cold water and dried in air, m.p. 110°; (Yield : 12.6 g ; 60%) ; $\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$ 2140 cm^{-1} (N=N=N), 1690 cm^{-1} (C=O).

Benzofuran- and 3-methylbenzofuran-2-carboxazides were similarly prepared from the respective acid chlorides and sodium azide.

General method for preparation of benzofuran-2-carbamates (I)

A solution of benzofuran-2-carboxazide (0.02 mole) in dry toluene (15 ml) was taken in a round-bottomed flask fitted with a condenser and heated in an oil bath at 70-80° till the evolution of nitrogen ceased (0.5 hr). To this, a solution of appropriate phenol (0.02 mole) in dry toluene (15 ml) was added and heating continued for 2-4 hr at 110°. The reaction mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure, diluted with pet. ether (40-60°) and cooled.

The crystalline products thus separated were filtered and recrystallized from chloroform-pet. ether as colourless to pale yellow shining crystals; $\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$ 3380 cm^{-1} (NH), 1720 cm^{-1} (ester C=O).

All the carbamates listed in Table 1 were prepared in a similar manner.

Preparation of benzofuran-2-carbamides (II)

A mixture of benzofuran-2-carboxazide (0.01 mol) and appropriate aniline (0.01 mol) in dry toluene (25 ml) was heated under reflux at 110° in an oil bath for 2-4 hr. During the course of the

TABLE I—ARYL BENZOFURAN, 3-METHYLBENZOFURAN AND 5-METHOXYBENZOFURAN-2-CARBAMATES (t)

No. R	R ₁	R ₂	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula*	Antibacterial activity (μg/ml)†						Antifungal activity (μg/ml)†										
						S.a	S.f	P.s.a	K.p	S.t	S.d	V.c	M.t	T.m	T.r	M.c	M.g	S.s	Cr.n	H.c		
1	H	H	116-20	66	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ NO ₂	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	50	100	50	100	>200	>200	>200	200	
2	H	4-Cl	164-66	50	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ ClNO ₂	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	100	200	100	200	>200	>200	>200	>200	100	
3	H	4-Br	178-80	81	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ BrNO ₂	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	200	200	100	200	>200	>200	>200	>200	100	
4	H	4-CH ₃	150-51	43	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ NO ₂	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	
5	H	3-CH ₃ ,4-Cl	158-60	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClNO ₂	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	25	100	>200	100	>200	>200	>200	>200	100	
6	H	2-Allyl,4-Cl	96-97	20	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClNO ₂	200	200	>200	200	200	200	100	25	50	50	100	100	100	100	100	100	
7	H	4-NO ₂	165-66	20	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₅	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	200	100	100	50	100	200	>200	>200	100	
8	H	3-CH ₃ ,5- CH(CH ₃) ₂	108-09	32	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ NO ₂	>200	50	>200	100	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	200
9	H	3-CH ₃ ,4-Cl, 6-CH(CH ₃) ₂	121-22	30	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ ClNO ₂	25	25	>200	>200	>200	>200	50	25	100	100	50	200	>200	>200	>200	>200	50
10	H	CH ₃ , H	120-21	78	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ NO ₂	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200
11	H	OH, 4-OH ₂	140	59	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ NO ₂	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200
12	H	CH ₃ , 3-CH ₃ ,4-Cl	145	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClNO ₂	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	100	200	200	100	200	200	200	200	200	200
13	H	CH ₃ , 3-CH ₃ , 6-CH(CH ₃) ₂	118	62	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ NO ₂	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200
14	H	CH ₃ , 3-CH ₃ ,4-Cl, 6-CH(CH ₃) ₂	128	66	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ ClNO ₂	>200	200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	25	200	100	200	200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200
15	5-OCH ₃	H	153-55	75	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ClNO ₄	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	<100	<100	<100	200	200	>200	>200	>200	>200	<100
16	5-OCH ₃	H	127-28	50	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ NO ₄	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	>200	<100
17	5-OCH ₃	H	145-47	70	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ ClNO ₄	100	50	>200	50	>200	200	<100	<100	<100	<100	<100	<100	<100	<100	<100	<100	<100

* All the compounds were analysed for C, H and N and the analytical results are within $\pm 0.4\%$ of the theoretical values.

† All these compounds were tested *in vitro* for antibacterial activity against S.a=S. aureus, S.f=S. faecalis, Ps.a=Ps. aeruginosa, K.p=K. pneumoniae, S.t=S. typhi, S.d=S. dysenteriae, V.c=V. cholerae, E.c=E. coli, A.t=A. tumefaciens, P.v=P. vulgaris, M.t=M. tuberculosis H₃₇Rv and antifungal activity against T.m=T. mentagrophytes, T.r=T. rubrum, M.c=M. canis, M.g=M. gypseum, E.f=E. floccosum, C.a=C. albicans, S.s=S. schenckii, Cr.n=Cr. neoformans, H.c=H. capsulatum and A.f=A. fumigatus and only the significant results are entered in the Table. The minimum inhibitory concentration was expressed in terms of micrograms per milliliter (μg/ml) at which the growth of the test organism was completely inhibited.

reaction crystalline products separated out in most of the cases. The reaction mixture was cooled, the solid was filtered, washed with fresh toluene (2 × 15 ml) and recrystallized from either acetone or alcohol. $\nu_{\max}^{\text{nujol}}$ 3350 cm^{-1} (NH); 1750 cm^{-1} (C=O).

All the carbamides reported in Table 2 were prepared in a similar manner.

3-methyl (compound no. 14) or 5-methoxy (compound no. 17) derivatives. The highest *in vitro* antifungal activity was shown by 2-allyl-4-chlorophenyl benzofuran-2-carbamate (compound no. 6) inhibiting the growth of seven out of ten fungi employed in the above screening at 50-100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. Four carbamates (compound nos. 5, 6, 9 & 14) were found to possess appreciable antituberculosis activity against *M. tuberculosis* H₃₇Rv at 25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

TABLE 2—ARYL BENZOFURAN AND 3-METHYLBENZOFURAN-2-CARBAMIDES (II)*

Sl. No.	R ₁	R ₂	M. P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula
1.	H	H	180-81	72	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂
2.	H	4-Cl	216-18	87	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂
3.	H	4-Br	230-32	73	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ BrN ₂ O ₂
4.	H	4-I	234-35	58	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ IN ₂ O ₂
5.	H	2,4-Cl ₂	202-03	83	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂
6.	H	4-CH ₃	214-15	95	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂
7.	H	3-CF ₃	161-63	21	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ F ₃ N ₂ O ₂
8.	H	2-CH ₃ ,4-Cl	230-31	75	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClN ₂ O ₂
9.	H	3-NO ₂ ,4-CH ₃	199-200	91	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₄
10.	CH ₃	H	229-30	76	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂
11.	CH ₃	4-Cl	237	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O ₂
12.	CH ₃	4-Br	245	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ BrN ₂ O ₂
13.	CH ₃	4-I	238	57	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ IN ₂ O ₂
14.	CH ₃	2,4-Cl ₂	239	72	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ Cl ₂ N ₂ O ₂
15.	CH ₃	4-CH ₃	232	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂
16.	CH ₃	3-CF ₃	212	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ F ₃ N ₂ O ₂
17.	CH ₃	2-CH ₃ ,4-Cl	215	66	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ClN ₂ O ₂
18.	CH ₃	3-NO ₂ ,4-CH ₃	214-16	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₄

* The compounds were analyzed for C, H and N and the analytical results are within ±0.4% of the theoretical values. All these compounds were subjected to *in vitro* antibacterial, antifungal, anti-amoebic and *in vivo* anthelmintic screening against all the micro-organisms listed under Table 1 and found to be inactive at test concentrations.

Biological Activity

All these benzofuran carbamates and carbamides were tested *in vitro* for antibacterial activity by serial dilution tube method and for antifungal activity by agar dilution assay method using various pathogenic test organisms according to the procedures previously described⁶. All the compounds were also tested for their *in vitro* anti-amoebic activity against *E. histolytica* and *in vivo* anthelmintic activity against *N. dubius* following the standard methods⁷. The screening results of all the compounds synthesised have been placed in Tables 1 & 2.

From the results it appears that whereas the aryl benzofuran carbamates possess some activity against various micro-organisms the corresponding carbamides are completely inactive. Some of the aryl benzofuran carbamates reported in this paper were found to possess moderate *in vitro* antibacterial and antifungal activities against representative organisms as shown in Table 1. Furthermore, it seems that introduction of a 3-methyl or a 5-methoxy substituent in the benzofuran ring causes a decrease in activity. Thus, 4-chlorothymyl benzofuran-2-carbamate (compound no. 9) showed the maximum *in vitro* antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, *S. faecalis*, *V. cholerae* and *M. tuberculosis* at 25-50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and is more active than the corresponding

Five aryl benzofuran-2-carbamates (compound nos. 1, 2, 5, 9 & 14) exhibited moderate *in vitro* anti-amoebic activity against *E. histolytica* at 125-250 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ while all the carbamides were inactive at test concentration (1000 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). None of these carbamates or carbamides showed any promising *in vivo* anthelmintic activity against *N. dubius* when tested in rats.

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